

Microbiome chracterization

A

B

Bacillota

- Christensenellales
- Lachnospirales
- Erysipelotrichales
- Oscillospirales
- Lactobacillales
- Acholeplasmatales
- RF39
- UBA4068
- TANB77

Bacteroidota

- Bacteroidales

Pseudomonadota

- Burkholderiales
- Rs-D84
- RF32

Cyanobacteriota

- Gastranaerophilales

Campylobacterota

- Campylobacteriales

Deferribacterota

- Deferribacterales

Desulfobacterota

- Desulfovibrionales

Verrucomicrobiota

- Verrucomicrobiales